

Goldbach's Problems

Khusid Mykhaylo

Pensioner, citizen of Ukraine, (Independent Researcher Wetzlar Germany.)

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 22 September 2023	The Goldbach-Euler binary problem is formulated as follows: Any even number, starting from 4, can be represented as the sum of two primes. The ternary Goldbach problem is formulated as follows: Every odd number greater than 7 can be represented as the sum of three odd primes, which was finally solved in 2013.[1]-[8]. In 1995, Olivier Ramare proved that any even number is the sum of no more than 6 primes.[9]
Corresponding Author: Khusid Mykhaylo	
KEYWORDS: solving, problems, in, number, theory	

THEOREM. Difference between any odd number and a prime odd number is equal to any even number and vice versa the difference of any even number and of a prime odd number is equal to any odd number.

Proof.

$$2K + 1 - p = 2N \quad (01)$$

Where $K = K_1, K_1 + 1, \dots, K_i = K_1 + i - 1, \dots, \infty$

$N = N_1, N_1 + 1, \dots, N_i = N_1 + i - 1, \dots, \infty$

P is a prime odd number. J - serial number of a continuous series of natural numbers, starting accordingly with K_1, N_1 . K and N are an infinite, continuous series of integers that begin with

K_1, N_1, p - any prime number (fixed value, some constant).

Thus we have (01). And similarly:

$$2N - p = 2K + 1 \quad (02)$$

the difference of any even and odd numbers and conversely allow to represent any prime odd number.

Corollary.

If the sum of six primes is any even number, then the sum of primes less than six is odd, any odd number, if even

any even number with corresponding initial values N_1, K_1 .

From the equality of the sum of six primes to any even number it follows:

$$P_1 + P_2 + P_3 + P_4 + P_5 + P_6 + 2 = P_7 + P_8 + P_9 + P_{10} + P_{11} + P_{12} \quad (03)$$

$$P_1 + P_2 + P_3 + P_4 + P_5 + P_6 - P_{12} + 2 = P_7 + P_8 + P_9 + P_{10} + P_{11} \quad (04)$$

$$2N - p + 2 = p_7 + p_8 + p_9 + p_{10} + p_{11} \quad (05)$$

$$2K + 1 = p_7 + \dots + p_{11} \quad (06)$$

$$p_7 + p_8 + p_9 + p_{10} + p_{11} + 2 = p_{12} + p_{13} + p_{14} + p_{15} + p_{16} \quad (07)$$

(the index under p is not critical)

$$P_1 + P_2 + P_3 + P_4 + 2 = P_5 + P_6 + P_7 + P_8 \quad (08)$$

$$P_1 + P_2 + P_3 + P_4 - P_8 + 2 = P_5 + P_6 + P_7 \quad (09)$$

$$P_5 + P_6 + P_7 = 2K + 1 \quad (10)$$

where $K = 3, 4, 5, \dots, \infty$

weak Goldbach problem.

$$P_1 + P_2 + P_3 + 2 = P_4 + P_5 + P_6 \quad (11)$$

$$P_1 + P_2 + P_3 - P_4 + 2 = P_5 + P_6 \quad (12)$$

$$P_5 + P_6 = 2N \quad (13)$$

where $N = 2, 3, \dots, \infty$

strong Goldbach problem.

REFERENCES

1. Terence Tao Google+ - Busy day in analytic number theory; - Harald Helfgott has...
2. Major arcs for Goldbach's, H.A. Helfgott // arxiv 1305.2897
3. Goldbach Variations // SciAm blogs, Evelyn Lamb, May 15, 2013.
4. Two Proofs Spark a Prime Week for Number Theory // Science 24 May, 2013.
5. Vol. 340 no. 6135 p. 913. Doi:10.1126/Science.340.6135.913
6. Weisstein, Eric W. *Goldbach*

“Goldbach's Problems”

Conjecture(English.)on the site Wolfram MathWorld.

7. *Yuri Matiyasevich. Hilbert's Tenth Problem: What was done and what is to be done.*
8. *de Polignac A. Recherches nouvelles sur les nombres premiers. 1849 .*
9. en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Olivier_Ramar